

IMPROVED DAMAGE TOLERANT FACE/CORE INTERFACE DESIGN IN SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

A face/core debond in a sandwich structure may propagate in the interface or kink into either the face or core depending on the mode-mixity of the loading. This study explores experimental methodologies for mapping the kinking behavior at various mode-mixities. Further, it is shown that the crack kinking behavior may be altered / avoided by changing the interface design by using Chopped Strand Mat (CSM), Continuous Filament Mat (CFM) and woven mats at the face/core interface as sources for fiber bridging, thus keeping and arresting the crack in the interface.

Keywords: Sandwich structures, crack kinking, fracture mechanics, mode-mixity, DCB-UBM

INTRODUCTION

A face/core debond crack in a sandwich structure can propagate self-similarly in the face/core interface or kink into either the face or core. The crack path is governed by the stress state at the crack tip (e.g. described by the mode-mixity) and the fracture toughness of the face, core and interface, see e.g. [1,2]. If the interface is sufficiently weak and brittle compared to the core and face laminate, the crack may propagate in the interface regardless of the mode-mixity. If on the other hand the interface is tough, the crack may kink into the core or face laminate. Thus, with regard to damage tolerance considerations, the “weakest link in the chain” should be identified, since the crack tends to propagate where the resistance is the least. Hence, the interface region should be carefully tailored in accordance with the fracture properties of the face, core and interface. Examples of crack paths in sandwich structures are schematically shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of possible crack propagation paths for a face/core crack in a sandwich structure. 1) In the interface, 2) crack kinks into core, and 3) crack kinks into face.

Crack propagation in the face/core interface or in the face laminate (multi-axial layers) may lead to bridging fibers that shields the crack tip by transferring stresses between the crack flanks hereby contributing to the energy dissipation. As large-scale bridging appears behind the crack tip, bridging may not have a significant influence on the crack kinking behavior, which is dictated by the stress state right in front of the interface crack tip. Conversely, since bridging is spread over a large area the energy dissipated by bridging may be large, so potentially the steady state fracture resistance of the face/core interface can be increased (by fiber bridging) without increasing the tendency for crack kinking out of the interface. This is useful for the purpose of keeping and arresting the crack in the interface, thus, improving the damage tolerance in sandwich structures.

The present paper uses the novel sandwich double cantilever beam specimen loaded by uneven bending moments (DCB-UBM) [1,3] to investigate the fracture behavior of various interface architectures as sources for fiber bridging, i.e. CSM and CFM mats. The DCB-UBM test method allows loading of the specimen at any desired mixed mode condition. Moreover, a finite element model is utilized to determine the relationship between applied moments and the mode-mixity.

ANALYSIS OF THE DCB-UBM TEST

The DCB-UBM sandwich specimen, test rig and loading condition are schematically shown in Fig. 2 [3,4].

Figure 2 Schematic of the loading principle of a DCB-UBM sandwich specimen

The moments, M_1 and M_2 , arise from a roller-wire system connected to the top edges of the specimen. The force in the wire is measured by a 5 kN capacity load cell. The load is applied by a single wire, thus ensuring equal forces acting on the rollers in the x-direction. The moments acting on the left and the right beam are determined from the wire tension, P , and the distances, l_1 and l_2 , between the rollers, see Fig. 2, thus

$$\begin{aligned} M_1 &= Pl_1 \\ M_2 &= Pl_2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are moments applied to the right and the left beams, both moments defined positive counterclockwise. The ratio M_1/M_2 is adjusted by changing the distances, l_1 and l_2 , between the rollers. Furthermore, the direction of the moments can be reversed by changing the mounting of the wire. If moments with opposite signs are applied, e.g. $M_1/M_2 = -1$, crack opening in the normal direction is dominating (mode I). Whereas, for moments with the same sign, the crack sliding in the tangential direction is dominating (mode II). To limit deflections and rotations of the beams 6 mm thick steel bars were bonded to the face sheets, see Fig. 3 [3,4].

Finite Element Analysis of the DCB-UBM Specimen

A 2-D plane strain finite element model was generated using the commercial finite element package ABAQUS [5] to determine the mode-mixity as a function of moment ratio M_1/M_2 . The crack is supposed to propagate along the lower face/core interface where cohesive elements are embedded between the continuum elements. In addition to the cohesive elements a frictionless contact interaction between the two bulk parts constituting the interface is formulated in a penalty master-slave configuration to prevent interpenetration of the crack flanks.

Figure 3 Geometry, loading and boundary conditions of the finite element model (upper) and b) mesh near the face/core interface (bottom)

The nodes on the right ends of the steel bars are fixed, while moments are applied to the left end, see Fig. 3 (upper). Due to the absence of rotational degree of freedom of the

continuum element, moments are applied to the specimen by introducing multi-point constraint (MPC) coupling between the nodes at the left steel edge in a master/slave configuration, so that moment loading applied to the master node will cause rotation of the entire edge. The mesh consists of both triangular and quadrilateral elements see Fig. 3 (bottom), with a refinement near the interface, where the smallest elements have a side length of 0.25 mm. The length of the cohesive elements in the interface is the same as the adjacent continuum elements and nodes are coincident. The cohesive zone must span several cohesive elements in order to get an accurate representation of the tractions and, furthermore, a sufficient number of continuum elements should be present through the beam thickness to accurately represent bending deformation [4]

The mode-mixity at the crack tip, ϕ , (here defined as $\phi = 2/\pi \tan^{-1}(\sigma_t/\sigma_n)$ [4]) is determined using the shear and normal stresses of the cohesive element at the crack tip, i.e. σ_t and σ_n respectively. It is important to point out that the mode-mixity varies from 0 to 1, where 0 corresponds to pure mode I and 1 to pure mode II. Due to the concept of loading by pure bending moments, the mode ratio at the crack tip is unchanged as the crack propagates and ϕ is approximately constant. Thus, each tested moment ratio M_1/M_2 can be associated with a fixed ϕ . However, the mode-mixity varies considerably between the crack tip and elsewhere in the process zone. To illustrate this behavior, Fig. 4 presents the numerical results for the mode-mixity as function of the x-coordinate inside the fracture process zone. Those results are for a specimen loaded at a moment ratio of $M_1/M_2=0$. Note that the variation of ϕ is large in the vicinity of the crack tip, whereas it is approximately constant far from the crack tip. Furthermore, ϕ is relatively mode II dominated at the crack tip and becomes increasingly mode I at distances away from the crack tip.

Figure 4 Numerically found mode-mixity ϕ as function of x-coordinate inside the process zone of a loaded DCB-UBM specimen after reaching steady state, $M_1/M_2=0$.

Face/core Interface

A DCB-UBM sandwich specimen containing a 20 mm thick H200 Divinycell foam core and fiberglass faces consisting of four DBLT quadric-axial mats and either a CSM or a CFM mat inserted between the DBLT layers and the core is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 Schematic illustration of the specimen lay-up and position of the pre-crack with CSM or CFM + woven mat in the interface.

Thus, in order to promote fiber bridging at the steady state fracture process, the following face/core interface alteration methods are elaborated below [4].

(1) Chopped strand mat (CSM). This mat consists of short randomly oriented fiber bundles. This configuration is used as reference to compare the effect of using methods (2) and (3) in the fiber bridging and kinking behavior of the DCB-UBM specimens.

(2) Continuous filament mat (CFM). A continuous filament mat (CFM) consists of long randomly oriented fiber bundles. Even though CFM mats have a density of 450 g/m^2 , the CFM layer is approximately 0.5 mm thicker, i.e. it contains more air. During the resin infusion process the resin fills out the air pockets and the extra thickness leads to a higher resin content of the CFM compared to the CSM.

(3) Woven layer. Preliminary tests indicated that the crack may kink into the adjacent laminate the loading is sufficiently mode II dominated. It is an aim of this study to limit this behavior by adding a woven mat to the face layup. The mat is a plain weave, a strand coarseness of tex-300 inserted between the CSM and the face [4]. The woven layer has relatively high in-plane tear and fracture toughness, which is believed to resist crack kinking into the adjacent laminate regardless of the crack propagation direction.

Photos of the CSM, CFM and woven mats can be seen in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 Photos of various laminates used in this study (unit on ruler is cm)

An idea for potentially increasing the fracture resistance of the interface without increasing the tendency for crack kinking into the adjacent face or core is shown schematically in Fig. 7 [4]. It is important to differ between crack initiation and propagation. The crack initiates as the crack driving force exceeds the energy required to open the pre-crack tip and propagate the crack incrementally. The initiation fracture

toughnesses for the face, core and interface with CSM mat are J_o^{face} , J_o^{core} and J_o^{CSM} respectively (if CFM is used, J_o^{CSM} will be J_o^{CFM}). In addition, subscripts *ss* mark the initiation steady state fracture process after crack initiation. As the crack propagates fibers may bridge the separating faces, which takes up part of the loading and thus increases the crack driving force necessary to propagate the crack further. The area where stresses are transferred between separating faces, e.g. by bridging fibers, is denominated the process zone. As the crack opening displacement becomes sufficiently large, fibers often start breaking in the wake of the process zone and a steady state situation is reached where the process zone translates self-similar as the crack propagates. When loading a sandwich specimen with a face/core crack the crack will tend to initiate where the crack tip fracture toughness is smallest, i.e. the smallest value of J_o^{face} , J_o^{core} and J_o^{CSM} , respectively. It is assumed that for the case without CSM, Fig. 7a, $J_o^{core} < J_o^{face}$ and it is likely that the crack will initiate in the core, with the energy release rate equal to J_o^{core} (since the process zone in the core is small $J_{ss}^{core} \approx J_o^{core}$). For the interface with CSM illustrated in Fig. 7b, $J_o^{CSM} < J_o^{core}$ and it is therefore likely that the crack will propagate in the CSM layer. However, the CSM layer entails fiber bridging and the fracture resistance increases to $J_{ss}^{CSM} > J_o^{core}$. The optimal interface layer for increasing the fracture resistance while avoiding crack kinking, is therefore one where the crack tip toughness is relatively small whereas the energy dissipated in the crack wake behind the crack tip should be relatively large.

Figure 7 Hypothetical fracture resistance curves for (a) interface without CSM and (b) interface with CSM. The steady state fracture toughness is equal to the crack driving force necessary to propagate the crack when the process zone has evolved.

Fracture Tests

Sandwich specimens with CSM, CFM and woven mats at the interface were tested under various moment ratios (M_1/M_2). In order to evaluate a wide range of mode

mixities, moment ratios were chosen such the mode-mixities varies from dominant mode I to dominant mode II. Three repetitions for each moment ratio were performed in order to get reliable results. The core material for all tested specimens was H200 foam core bonded to DBLT multiaxial face sheets with the interface modifications stated above. The face/core pre-crack was artificially created by placing a non-adhesive film insert at the face/core interface during the manufacturing process of specimens. Thus, the initial crack location was right in the face/core interface. Prior to conducting the fracture tests a speckled pattern is applied to the specimen surface by using first white and subsequently black spray paint. The speckled pattern allows tracking of the full-field displacements using a commercial digital image correlation (DIC) system, ARAMIS 2M [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The test method by pure bending moments entails that the J integral depends only on applied moments, elastic properties and specimen geometry. The J integral is evaluated from the applied moments using laminated beam theory [4]. Furthermore, full-field displacement measurements are recorded by the DIC system, and the displacement of the pre-crack tip is extracted from the measurements and separated in normal (δ_n) and tangential (δ_t) opening components [4]. Figure 8 shows the J integral (J_R) vs. the effective pre-crack tip opening $\delta^* = \sqrt{\delta_t^2 + \delta_n^2}$ for a specimen with H200 core, CSM mat at the interface and loaded under $M_1/M_2 = 0$.

Figure 8 Measured and extracted data (J_R vs. opening at the pre-crack tip location) from a single DCB-UBM test with $M_1/M_2 = 0$ and CSM mat at the face/core interface.

As observed in Fig. 8, initially J_R increases rapidly, with only very small opening of the pre-crack tip. As the applied J_R value exceeds the fracture toughness of the material, the crack propagates and the pre-crack tip opens. Bridging fibers connect the separating faces and as a result the fracture resistance increases meaning that a larger crack driving force (J_R) is needed to propagate the crack. Assuming that the specimen is loaded monotonically with constant mode-mixity, the process zone eventually reaches a steady-state condition where the fracture resistance reaches a plateau. Thus, improving the fracture resistance due to large-scale fiber bridging that arrests the crack at the interface.

It is observed from the tests that often the crack does not propagate in a stable manner, but in jumps of 3-5 cm. This is the reason for the drops in J_R observed in Fig. 8. Since the moment of loading at the crack tip is not affected by crack length, the observed unstable crack growth is caused by either material variations along the interface, or rate dependent fracture properties. However, these phenomena are out of the scope in the present study. A photo of a cracked specimen (CFM mat at the interface) with large scale fiber bridging is seen in Fig. 9.

Figure 9 Specimen with a CFM layer loaded at a mode-mixity of $\phi = 0.39$, the crack is propagating in the CFM layer under large-scale bridging

As discussed in connection with Fig. 7, the crack may propagate in three basic ways: (1) the crack stays in the CSM or CFM layer, (2) the crack kinks into the core or (3) the crack kinks into the face. For the materials used in the present study all three regimes can be obtained by varying the moment ratio M_1/M_2 . If the crack kinks into the face laminate the crack gradually jumps from one layer to the next, and the distance (in the crack propagation direction) between points where the crack changes layer varies between 2 and 10 cm. Figure 10 shows a photo of a specimen with a crack gradually kinking through the laminate. It should be noted how the crack initially propagates between the CSM and the core for 2-3 cm, then in the CSM, then in the -45° layer and finally in the 0° layer. The 0° layer is not penetrated, but in some experiments the crack jumps to the other side of the 0° layer without breaking the fibers. A schematic illustration of the crack path is shown at the bottom of Fig. 10.

Figure 10 Photo and schematic illustration of loaded DCB-UBM specimen with CSM mat in the interface. A crack is gradually kinking through the CSM and face layers. The moment ratio is $M_1/M_2 = 0.2$ and $\phi = 0.98$ at the crack tip

Generally, the fracture resistance as function of the pre-crack tip opening behaves as the plot shown in Fig. 7 where J initially increases steeply, then as the crack propagates fiber bridging may develop, leading to rising fracture resistance until a plateau is reached where $J = J_{ss}$. The steady state fracture resistance J as a function of various mode-mixities at the crack tip is plotted in Fig. 11 for the following cases: a) CSM (reference case), b) CFM, c) CSM + woven, d) CFM + woven. The x-symbol is used to mark results where the crack propagated in the CSM or CFM layer, the o-symbol indicates that the crack kinked into the face, and the Δ -symbol indicates crack kinking into the core. The \square -symbol marks the load-cases where the crack grows in the resin between the CSM or CFM layer and the woven, but did not cross the woven layer. The approximate transition where the crack starts to kink into the adjacent face (quadraxial layers) is marked with a vertical dashed line.

Figure 11 Steady state fracture resistance as a function of mode-mixity for tested specimens. The x-symbol indicates crack propagation in the CSM or CFM layer, the \square -symbol marks crack propagation in the interface between the woven and the CSM

For the CSM layer in Fig. 11a four mode-mixities at the crack tip are considered, $\phi = \{0.14, 0.64, 0.84, 0.99\}$. For two out of four specimens loaded by the mode-mixity $\phi = 0.84$, the crack kinks into the face, whereas for all other specimens the crack stays in the

CSM layer. As the crack kinks into the face the fracture resistance increases substantially, for $\varphi=0.84$ and 0.99 . Results for the CFM layer are shown in Fig. 11b, for the mode-mixities $\varphi = \{0.14, 0.39, 0.64, 0.84\}$. In contrast to the specimens with CSM, a mode-mixity of $\varphi = 0.14$ leads to crack kinking into the core, with a measured fracture toughness of approximately 2.7 kJ/m^2 , which corresponds approximately to the measured mode I fracture toughness of the core (2.5 kJ/m^2). At a mode-mixity of $\varphi = 0.39$ the crack propagates in the CFM layer with large-scale bridging and a steady state fracture resistance between 2.0 and 2.3 kJ/m^2 . For the final two tested mode-mixities ($\varphi = 0.64$ and 0.84) the crack kinked into the face, at much increased fracture resistance compared to crack propagation in the CFM layer.

CSM + woven specimens were tested at $\varphi = \{0.22, 0.39, 0.49, 0.64, 0.84, 0.99\}$ and only the mode-mixity of 0.99 showed kinking into the face, see Fig. 11c. At a mode I dominated loading ($\varphi \approx 0.22$), the crack propagated in the centre of the CSM, resulting in relatively dense fiber bridging, whereas a mode-mixity of $\varphi \approx 0.64$ made the crack propagate in the outer region of the CSM with less fiber bridging, and consequently less fracture resistance. The results for the CFM + woven configuration shown in Fig. 11d illustrates a somewhat different behavior compared to that of the CSM in Fig. 11c. Here a mode I dominated loading leads to crack propagation between the core and the CFM layer. Only at more mode II dominated loadings does the crack starts to kink into the CFM layer which results in increased fiber bridging and fracture resistance.

In the conducted experiments the woven layer is never penetrated by the crack and to some degree the woven layer succeeds in preventing the crack from kinking into the face, denoted by \square -symbol in Figs. 11c and 11d. However, for mode II dominated cases, a secondary crack is initiated on the opposite side of the woven layer, and this crack continues to propagate in the interface between the woven and face without breaking the woven mat, see photo in Fig. 12.

Figure 12 Crack jumping to the opposite side of the woven layer without penetration. The specimen shown is CSM + woven loaded at $M_1/M_2 = 0.3$, $\varphi = 0.84$ at the crack tip.

CONCLUSIONS

Face/core interface modifications using CSM, CFM and woven mats as sources for fiber bridging in sandwich structures were examined. Experimental results showed large-scale fiber bridging at the face/core interface which acted as a crack arrested mechanism, and thus improving the damage tolerance of sandwich structures. With respect to kinking into the face it was partially avoided when using CSM + woven at

mode mixities less than $\phi = 0.99$, whereas minor success was observed when using CFM + woven. Moreover, larger interface toughnesses for specimens with CFM with/without woven mats were observed when compared to specimens with CSM mats. Finally, despite of the partial success in avoiding kinking by modifying the face/core interface; the current study provides a design window for interface design modifications in sandwich structures.

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